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Effects of Critical Thinking Strategies on Students' Written Composition Performance in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on effects of critical thinking strategies on students' written composition performance in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria. The paper investigated the effects of using critical thinking strategies in developing essay writing among students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kaduna States, Nigeria. For the purpose of this study three research objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated. The sample of the study consisted of two groups the experimental with 57 students while the control with 56 students. The instrument used was essay question. Both validity and reliability were checked by the researcher. The study may be significant to students, Teachers, curriculum planners. The study covers only Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kaduna States, Nigeria). The study used chi – square to test the research hypotheses at alpha level of 0.05 between the experimental and the control groups.

Keywords: Critical thinking, written composition, students, essay writing

INTRODUCTION

Writing is the most important language skill and the most sophisticated one, as it obeys rules and instructions. This is really true considering the efforts learners make to enhance their writing, and make words convey their thoughts in an understandable way. Despite the important role of writing in learning and communicating, both native and non native students argue that it is very difficult to master. The ability to write accurately and effectively is a problem that evades many students. Students at the tertiary level are intended to learn how to write different types of assignments. In teaching a foreign la language, writing is considered as the most problematic skill. It is agreed that the writing skill is diff cult even for native students because it requires many processes and steps to be mastered. writing. In its broad sense, it means “not only putting one’s thoughts to paper as they occur, but actually using writing to create new knowledge”. (Weigle, 2002).

Generally, writing is interpreted as the act of tracing symbols on a paper using a pen or pencil. The way students write, even at the tertiary level, is indicative of their poor academic background, which is a carry-over from the secondary level. This is evidenced by the students' observed gross incompetence in their written compositions, which fail to satisfy the major criteria for good composition writing, recording speech, even though it must be acknowledged as secondary medium of communication. Writing is one of the major skills for using language, through which one can convey his thoughts. It is stated that "writing is a reflection of what can occur only after the main ideas are in place." (Clark, 2003). This means that the

writer's goal is to know how to say what has been discovered, not in discovering and selecting what to say. Flower (1989) states that writing is a process that can be influenced by some elements in the learning activities. He says that: Writing is a social act that can only occur within a specific situation. It is therefore influenced both by the personal attitudes and social experiences that the writer brings to writing and the impacts of the particular political and institutional context in which it interviews, analyses of surrounding practices and other techniques, researchers seek to develop more complete accounts to local writing contexts. Hyland (2003) defines it as "marks on a page or a screen, a coherent arrangement of words, clauses, and sentences, structured according to a system of rules" According to Zamel (1992) writing is the combination of various cognitive operations which is consciously produced, revised, adapted and corrected. Many researchers agreed on the social nature of the writing skill. In addition to that, the writer has to keep in mind: content, organization, grammar, syntax, mechanics, word choice, audience, purpose and the writing process. The combination of all these components makes writing a difficult skill. Writing is a very complex skill that demands both physical and mental activity from the part of the writer. Many cognitive psychologists have described it as the most complex demanding of all cognitive activities undertaken by human beings. To sum up, writing is the transformation of our thoughts into language. Writing is a creative process of transmitting and communicating ideas that demands many factors in order.

These criteria include content, organization, expression, and mechanical accuracy, all of which are very poor. In terms of content, most students often stray from the subject matter of their compositions. They frequently deviate to entirely different areas that have no relevance to the topic. It is not uncommon to see students writing about a birthday party when the question asks them to write about a child naming ceremony. This is because some of these students do not understand the requirements of the question in the first place. Considering the level of incompetency observed in students' essays, the aforementioned errors are a result of their inability to generate ideas, think critically, and develop a positive attitude towards composition writing. This situation has reached a degree of incompetency that calls for concern and necessitates urgent research efforts Critical thinking has become a crucial educational goal, as students require strong thinking skills to utilize reasoning and logic when analyzing arguments for problem-solving and decision-making (Pither & Soden, 2001) Critical thinking encompasses both skills and disposition. Critical Thinking Skills (CTS) focus on cognitive abilities such as interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and self-regulation. On the other hand, Critical Thinking Disposition (CTD) relates to the affective domain, including qualities such as inquisitiveness, systematically, analyticity, truth-seeking, open-mindedness, self-confidence, and maturity (Facione, Facione & Sanchez, 1994).

Researchers such as Facione & Sanchez have emphasized the importance of teaching critical thinking skills to students, as they are essential for academic success in college, professional careers, and social life. With this in mind, the study specifically explores critical thinking through writing, among other types of writing, such as argumentative compositions.

Written composition is the way in which a writer structures a piece of writing, utilizing content and paragraph development, organization, expression, and mechanical accuracy to effectively convey their message. A paragraph, on the other hand, is a self-contained unit of discourse in writing that focuses on a specific point or idea. Organization is crucial throughout the writing process, as it ensures that ideas are presented in a regular, predictable, and coherent manner. The use of Pre-writing techniques can aid in planning the work effectively before starting to write. Expression involves the process of conveying one's thoughts and ideas through written language, which is more systematic and complex compared to verbal expression. Mechanical accuracy, including indentation, capitalization, and punctuation, plays a significant role in producing an effective piece of writing.

Based on these considerations, the paper aims to conduct an experimental study focusing on tertiary institution students, specifically in Kaduna and Kastina in North Western states. These students will be trained on critical thinking strategies, and developing a positive attitude towards applying these techniques for effective composition writing. The paper aims to determine whether the treatment given to

the students will positively impact their writing composition tasks, which will be further analyzed through the results obtained.

Statement of the Problem

This paper aims to examine the effects of critical thinking strategies on students' performance in written composition, specifically Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria. In Nigeria, English language serves not only as the language of administration, law, commerce, and religious activities but also as the language of instruction from primary to tertiary institutions. Unfortunately, it has been observed with deep concern that the written composition tasks of our students in tertiary institution particularly in the proposed study area is drastically poor. Most English students, in Colleges of Education, possess a weak performance in the writing skill. Due to the complexity of this skill, learners find it difficult to master all aspects of writing. We believe that students need to be provided with more efficient writing strategies to overcome the difficulties they face when writing. The poor attitude of students towards exploring effective writing techniques may contribute to this struggle. Many students are unwilling to learn and acquire the skills necessary for producing effective written compositions. Therefore, it is crucial to train tertiary institution students, specifically those in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Katsina States, Nigeria, in critical thinking strategies, and fostering positive attitudes towards applying these strategies in writing composition. By conducting a study and analyzing the results, we can determine whether the treatment and training provided to the students have beneficial effects on their writing composition skills.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to

Examine the effects of critical thinking strategies on the students' written composition performance of Colleges of Education students of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria with the aim of improving their writing abilities. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To determine the effect of critical thinking strategies on content in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria.
2. To explore the effect of critical thinking strategies on organization in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study in understanding the effects of critical thinking strategies on essay writing performance of Students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States Nigeria.

1. To what extent do critical thinking strategies have effects on content in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of critical thinking strategies on organization in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The study proposes the following null hypotheses that was tested at 0.05 significance level

H0₁: There is no significant effect of critical thinking strategies on content in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria:

H0₂: There is no significant effect of critical thinking strategies on organization in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Preamble

This chapter aims to review the existing literature on the effect of critical thinking strategies on students' performance in written composition among Colleges of Education students of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria.

Critical Thinking

Critical thinking skills are used every day, both consciously and unconsciously, by most people in their daily lives. For example, students at tertiary institutions need to employ critical thinking skills in their reading and demonstrate these skills in their writing. In 1940, Sumner defined critical thinking as follows: "A critical thinker is inquisitive, analytical, and open-minded. Critical thinking involves reading and writing critically. Writing critically means presenting your conclusions in a clear and well-reasoned manner to persuade others." When one engages in critical thinking, they analyze by breaking things down, synthesize by bringing parts together in a coherent way, and evaluate by making judgments based on sound evidence. Therefore, critical thinkers pay attention to details, consider different viewpoints, and evaluate their own position. They develop an accurate understanding of an issue and can identify trends and predict outcomes. Additionally, critical thinkers consider broad implications and long-term consequences.

Cottrell (2005) describes critical thinking as a cognitive activity that focuses on argumentation and requires the use of the mind. Facione (2000) characterizes critical thinking as a self-adjusting process that involves the use of cognitive skills to make judgments and improve upon them.

According to Facione (2000), possessing skills enables us to perform better. In the case of thinking skills, they can improve the quality of thinking and facilitate more effective thinking. Fisher (2001:8) also describes in detail the important critical thinking skills, which include the abilities to:

6. Identify the elements in a reasoned case, especially reasons and conclusions.
7. Identify and evaluate assumptions.
8. Clarify and interpret expressions and ideas.
9. Judge the acceptability and credibility of claims.
10. Evaluate arguments of different kinds.
11. Analyze, evaluate, and make decisions.
12. Draw inferences.
13. Produce arguments.

Although a consensual agreement on the taxonomy of critical thinking skills has not been reached, this study adopts the core set of critical thinking skills proposed by McGregor (2007), many of which have been included in the critical thinking taxonomy provided by researchers (Wen, Wang, Zhao, Liu, Wang, 2009; Cottrell, 2005; Fisher, 2001; Halper, 1998). According to Chafee (cited by Facione, 2000), a critical thinker is not merely someone who can reflect, explore, and analyze, but also someone who chooses to think in advanced and sophisticated ways (p.65). To become a critical thinker, internal motivation, also widely known as disposition, is needed (Miri, David, Uri, 2007; Giancarlo & Facione, 2004). For the purpose of this study, a student with a strong disposition towards critical thinking is one who demonstrates an active willingness to engage in thinking and persist in challenging and complex thinking tasks (Halper, 1998). Facione (2000) advocates for the importance of developing a disposition towards critical thinking because understanding a person's disposition allows us to predict how they are likely to act or react in a variety of circumstances (p.63). A person with critical thinking skills may fail to utilize them, while someone with a disposition towards critical thinking will embrace opportunities to engage in it, even if their level of critical thinking skills is low (Ip et al., 2000).

However, without the willingness to think critically, one is less likely to do so in practice, regardless of their ability. In summary, critical thinking is crucial in education as it serves as an essential tool for inquiry, problem-solving, and making informed decisions (Simpson & Courtney, 2002). Therefore, students should actively participate in learning activities, apply their knowledge to solve academic and social problems, and analyze and organize information to make informed decisions. Additionally, by incorporating critical thinking into learning and social practices, students can become more open-minded and creative in finding the most effective methods of learning and problem-solving (Tiwari, Lai, So, 2006). Thus, one of the aims of this study is to develop students' critical thinking skills and increase their

disposition towards critical thinking, enabling them to apply these skills effectively in both their academic and social lives.

Critical Writing

Critical writing does not necessarily involve writing about a topic in a negative way; it simply requires considering all sides of the argument. For instance, when conducting research, you are likely to come across different authors with varying viewpoints. A critical writer's task is to take into account all of these perspectives in their essay, demonstrating their awareness of the range of issues associated with the topic. The key characteristics of critical writing include:

1. A clear and confident refusal to accept the conclusions of other writers without evaluating the arguments and evidence they provide.
2. A balanced presentation of reasons why the conclusions of other writers may either be accepted or approached with caution.
3. A clear presentation of your own evidence and arguments, leading to your own conclusion
4. Recognition of limitations in your own evidence, arguments, and conclusions.

Critical writing involves developing one's own academic voice within a specific subject area. It is a process that requires reflection, explanation of opinions, and the use of critical and creative thinking to compare choices, seek possible solutions, provide support, and clarify ideas. Engaging in writing can help develop relevant thinking and cognitive skills and contribute to the development of relevant mental processes. According to Bean (2001: 17), writing "requires analytical or argumentative thinking and is characterized by a controlling statement and a logical, hierarchical structure."

Similarly, Schfermen (1991) cited Norshidrah (2012:7) to explain that writing forces students to organize their thoughts, contemplate their topic, evaluate their data in a logical fashion, and present their conclusions persuasively. Therefore, good writing is a reflection of good critical thinking. In turn, effective thinking can also contribute to effective writing. Writing is a cognitive process influenced by higher mental functions to which it is connected (Surd, 2011). Since writing is a written form of speech, the results of thinking determine how language is used. Critical thinking enables learners to gather relevant knowledge and thoughts, incorporate personal understanding and values, select and integrate useful information, and construct knowledge to create meaning.

Writing is also a process of metacognition, which can promote effective thinking (Larkin, 2009). We use cognitive skills to complete a task, and metacognitive skills can be used to reflect on the process of cognition, serving as monitors and regulators of this mental process later on (Flavell et al., 2002). Hacker, Keener, and Kircher (2009) claim that writing can be seen as applied metacognition, stating that reading, re-reading, and reviewing are monitoring strategies for our own thoughts, while editing, drafting, idea generation, word production, translation, diagnosing, and revision are used as control strategies for our thoughts. Monitoring and controlling our thinking is metacognition (Hacker, Keener, and Kircher, 2009). In view of the above, critical writing is a process that involves using a range of writing skills as well as personal qualities.

Paul & Elder (2007) state that during the process of writing, writers need to adjust and monitor their thinking to seek useful information and assess its relevance and significance for achieving their writing goals. This writing process encourages students to think critically and continuously refine their ideas, gradually acquiring more effective ways of adjusting and controlling their thoughts. Metacognition is also essential in improving writing, as it helps writers find better and more effective ways of thinking about their writing, developing ideas, and learning from others (Paul & Elder, 2007). Additionally, while many people find critical writing challenging, students often discover it to be a creative process once they better understand the necessary skills.

Olson (1992), as cited in Norshidrah (2012), argues that thinking can be defined through pre-writing, writing, revising, and editing activities. This means that as writers engage in the writing process, they use their judgment to evaluate their own text and make any necessary changes to express their ideas clearly and confidently to readers. Thus, engaging students in critical thinking during academic writing classes is crucial, but it can only be achieved if the writing assignments foster such work (Reynolds & Moskowitz,

2008). Therefore, the ability to think critically extends beyond understanding the writer's message; it also involves evaluating the validity of the message is valid or not

Critical Thinking and Education

Resistance to the possibility of teaching critical thinking is often related to context, particularly in Asian and Nigerian countries, as well as in L2 classes. On one hand, some scholars claim that critical thinking is itself a Western phenomenon (Ramanathan & Kaplan, 1996a; Fox, 1994). Therefore, it is difficult to teach it to members of a society where critical thinking does not exist. Moreover, in education, teachers are considered authorities in the classroom, and students are expected to be obedient to authority (Yang, Badger, Yu, 2006; Little Wood, 2000; Liv, 1998). Consequently, students are encouraged to pay careful attention to the teacher, enabling them to develop questioning skills based on the presented material. This, in turn, will help them become critical thinkers without jumping to conclusions." According to Vygotsky, the concept of the zone of proximal development (ZPD) distinguishes between a student's actual development level and their potential level (Oakley, 2004). Each student has the ability to develop their skills from a virtual level to a potential level at any given time. Vygotsky believed that students could enhance their capacity for critical thinking and improve their achievements if they receive assistance from experts. These experts can support students in developing their critical thinking abilities. One strategy for fostering critical thinking is by allowing students to express their ideas. Critical thinking is a fundamental skill that enhances the learning environment. Various teaching and learning methods are employed, taking into consideration the pedagogic context and the development stages of critical thinking (Florea & Hurjui, 2014).

Florea and Hurjui, (2014) define critical thinking as an approach to problem-solving that involves persuasive, logical, and rational arguments. It involves verifying data, evaluating processes, and selecting appropriate solutions for a given task. Students should be able to critically analyze incorrect answers and provide alternative solutions based on sound reasoning.

Based on the research conducted by Moon (2004), critical thinking is an active and complex process that involves various activities such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening. It requires individuals to think critically to accumulate knowledge and arrive at effective solutions. Critical thinking is a result that stems from an individual's own thinking process. It involves associating new concepts with existing knowledge as a basic step.

Teaching critical thinking to Nigerian students may pose a challenge to teachers' authority, as it encourages students to evaluate information rather than accepting it without question. Moon (2004) further explains that thinking critically involves examining information from multiple sources, processing it in a creative and rational manner, and analyzing and drawing conclusions from it. The resulting knowledge needs to be constructed and can be defended and justified considering the changing context and meaning. Although Moon (2004) identifies several activities for promoting critical thinking, the specific ideas and approaches may vary among different teachers and their chosen activities.

4. One activity for promoting critical thinking is reviewing other people's arguments: In this case, the task of the critical thinker is to analyze and assess the process of developing an argument and reaching conclusions. During group discussions, such as speaking and writing activities, students can engage in reviewing someone else's argument to complete a task. This activity encourages students to examine the strengths and weaknesses of different arguments, evaluate the evidence and reasoning presented, and form their own informed judgments. It helps develop their ability to think critically and engage in thoughtful discussions.
5. Evaluation of an object: The students should think critically in forming an evaluative judgment of an object such as a work of art, a form of task presentation, and so on step, the critical thinker must think creatively. Furthermore, they can evaluate an object that has been developed by others.
6. Development of an argument: In this stage, the argument is built by a critical thinker such as preparing the presentation with his/her own words, reasoning and decision making. However, the students often face issues when presenting their arguments, especially a lack of structure in writing or speaking. Further, more, the student should use this process in other task that will they

do.

7. Thinking critically about oneself: This term is often expressed as well-known learning reflection or reflecting critically, (Brock & McGill, Fisher as cited in Moon, 2004) even though it could be focused on activity by improving the new idea. Because the self is connected to any other forms of critical thinking, the issues relevant in critical thinking about the self can be a part of other forms of thinking critically.
8. Analyzing the case: The teacher often demands that the student think critically about what is happening during the learning process. The purpose of this step is to involve the student in reviewing their activities and thinking how matters have been managed by them. Moreover, it will consist of thinking critically about self. As a result, the students become more reactive to every single event that happens to them.
9. Participation in developing answers to the argument of others opinions perform the next action in thinking critically: Here, the students most think deeply to examine the background of the argument and how to respond to it. In addition, they can respond to the argument by speaking or writing.

In other words the student can use many ways to present their opinions on the other hand, it may also be difficult for ESL/ EFL students with low proficiency to engage in critical thinking in English classes. L2 students tend to use memorization as their main strategy in learning English (Shahini & Riazi 2011). When they are writing in English they often retrieve though and linguistic forms from their memory and write these down (Larkin 2003). They are less likely to create meaning and reconstruct linguistic terms. As a result, their engagement in critical thinking can be impaired. For this reason, Atkinson 1997, there is less need for the teacher to create opportunities for students to rehearse and perfect it. However, in many countries as such opportunities would seem to be more valuable for students, owing to the lack of emphasis on critical thinking in their cultures.

Empirical Studies

In Yang et al's (2008) study, it was found that Web-Based Bulletin Board discussions contributed to improvements in critical thinking among university students. The students reported a positive attitude towards the instruction, and they mentioned that the opportunity to engage with peers allowed them to ask for help, share views, and examine their own opinions. The study also revealed that students were more willing to share ideas and evaluate their own opinions in this collaborative online environment.

In Quitadamo's (2009) study, the effect of peer-led team learning (PLTL), a small group learning method that promotes discourse and creative problem-solving, on critical thinking in undergraduate science courses was investigated. The California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) by Facione (1990b) was utilized to determine students' level of critical thinking. The results from a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test control group design revealed that there was a significantly higher gain in critical thinking observed among the PLTL students compared to the non-PLTL group.

In Wichadee's (2014) study, the effect of a learning management system (LMS) as a tool to facilitate students' writing and critical thinking skills in Thailand was examined. The primary data included students' online learning records and forum discussion postings. The findings indicated that students' motivation to learn was at a high level, and their motivation was positively correlated with their learning behavior. There were no significant differences found between male and female students in terms of motivation and learning behavior. The use of the LMS enhanced students' writing skills, encouraged critical thinking, and helped them write in a more systematic manner.

These studies highlight the positive impact of specific instructional methods, such as peer-led team learning and the use of learning management systems, on critical thinking development among undergraduate science students and writing and critical thinking skills among students in Thailand. Both studies demonstrate the potential of innovative teaching approaches in fostering critical thinking abilities and facilitating learning outcomes.

The study conducted by Alufohai (2016) focused on investigating grammatical errors in written compositions in selected secondary schools in Owan West Local Government Area of Edo State.

One research question was formulated to provide direction for the study. A descriptive survey design was employed for the research. The target population comprised 2,196 junior secondary school students from public and private schools in Owan West Local Government Area. A sample of 180 students was selected using random sampling techniques. These students were given an essay prompt on the topic "How I spent Christmas holiday." The written compositions were evaluated based on criteria such as content, organization, mechanical accuracy, and expression. Simple percentages were used to analyze the students' performance. The analysis revealed that many students struggled to develop the essential topic and organize their essays effectively. Additionally, there were challenges in differentiating between the use of present tense and past tense. The findings of the study led to recommendations, with one suggestion being the employment of qualified English teachers in junior secondary schools to improve English language instruction.

In Oladotun's (2019) study, the effect of explicit instructional strategy and cognitive styles on the achievement of senior secondary school students in summary writing was examined. The study employed a pretest and post-test design, which lasted for a duration of eight weeks. The results indicated that explicit instruction and cognitive style had significant effects on students' achievement in summary writing. Based on these findings, it was concluded that the utilization of explicit instruction and cognitive styles in language pedagogy holds great potential for enhancing achievement in summary writing. The strategy encouraged active participation of students through practice sessions and corrective feedback.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

For this study, a quasi-experimental design with a pre-test and post-test was adopted. This design involved three groups: one experimental groups and one control group.

Population of the Study

The population of this research consists of all public tertiary institutions and their students in North-Western, Nigeria. It comprised of seven states, all of which have universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, nursing schools, and other institutions classified as tertiary.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for this study consists of two state-owned Colleges of Education (COEs) from the seven in the North-western, Nigeria, with a total of 273 students across the Colleges of Education. Kaduna State College of Education and Isah Kaita College of Education, Kastina for the experimental and control groups.

Instrumentation

A reliability analysis was conducted on the perceived value scales of the instrument. The results indicated that the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the instrument was 0.72, which suggests a reliable instrument. The researcher used Essay Question to measure For the Written Composition Performance of the students. This was administered to both the experimental and control groups.

Procedure for Data Collection

The data collected was in two folds pre and post test with the support of two research assistants. Kaduna State College of Education, Kaduna for the experimental group was given pre test within 1 week and the control group of Isa Kaita College of Education, Kastina Was given the same 1 week. However, treatment package was given to the experimental of Kaduna State College of Education, Kaduna while the control group was thought using conventional method after that post test follows immediately.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected in this study, which focused on the effects of critical thinking strategies on students' written composition performance in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria, was analyze using descriptive statistics; means and standard deviations, to answer the research questions while t-test was use in testing null hypotheses. By employing these statistical methods, the researcher aim to gain a comprehensive understanding of the data and assess the variables under investigation.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect on critical thinking strategies and the lecture method in the content performance of the essay writing of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastinsa States, Nigeria

Table 1: Independence T-test Statistic on Difference between Critical Thinking and Lecture Method in the Mean Content Performance of the Essay Writing of Students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria.

Study Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean difference	df	t computed	P
Critical thinking	29	5.1034	61788				
				1.532	83	8.428	0.000
Lecture method	56	3.5714	87089				

$P = 0.000 > 1.96$, $t_{\text{computed}} = 8.428 < 1.96 t_{\text{critical}}$ at $df = 83$

Result of the table 2 shows the comparison between critical thinking and the lecture method on content of essay writing. The P value of 0.000 for content shows significant difference exist among critical thinking and lecture method in favour of the Experimental Group. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that :”There is no significant effect on critical thinking strategies and the lecture method in the content performance of the essay writing of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria” is hereby rejected and replaced by alternate hypothesis that there is significant difference that exist between the Critical thinking strategies and lecture method in the content performance of the essay writing of the students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect on critical thinking strategies and Lecture method on organization in the essay writing performance of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria

Table 2: Independent T-test Statistic on the Difference between Critical Thinking and Lecture Method on Organization in the Essay Writing Performance of Students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States. Nigeria.

Study Group	N	Mean	Std	df	Mean difference	t computed	p
Critical thinking	29	4.8276	.75918				
				83	.8454	4.804	0.000
Lecture method	56	3.9821	.77439				

$P = 0.000 > 1.96$, $t_{\text{computed}} = 4.804 < 1.96 t_{\text{critical}}$ at $df = 83$

Result of the table shows the comparison between critical thinking and the lecture methods on organization in the essay writing performance of students. The P value of 0.000 lower than 0.005 alpha level of significance while it computed value of 4.814. This implies that critical thinking experimental group performance significantly than the lecture method. Consequently, the null hypothesis that state that there is no significant difference between critical thinking and lecture method on organization in the essay writing performance of student in Colleges of Education pf Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria is hereby rejected.

1. There is no significant difference between critical thinking and lecture method in the content performance of the essay writing of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States., Nigeria their mean content performance for critical thinking for experimental group 2 and lecture method were $P=0.000 < 1.96$, $T_{\text{computed}} = 8.428 > 1.96 t_{\text{critical}}$ at $df = 83$.
2. There is no significant difference between critical thinking and lecture method in the

organization performance of the essay writing of students in Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Katsina States, Nigeria. Their mean organization performance for critical thinking and lecture method were $P=0.000 < 1.96$, t computed 4.804, 1.96, critical at df 83.10.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the implementation of critical thinking strategies has a positive effect on students' written composition performance of Colleges of Education of Kaduna and Kastina States, Nigeria. The study found that these strategies significantly improved various aspects of essay writing, including content, organization, expression, and mechanical accuracy.

The results indicated that students who were exposed to critical thinking strategies demonstrated higher performance levels in all these areas compared to the control group. The findings also align with previous research and literature on the topic, highlighting the importance of these strategies in enhancing writing skills among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are put forth:

1. Encourage and motivate teachers to incorporate critical thinking strategies into their English language instruction, specifically in the teaching of writing. Provide professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in utilizing these strategies effectively.
2. Emphasize the importance of content in essay writing and composition through teacher training and curriculum development. Provide teachers with instructional materials and strategies to teach these skills explicitly.
3. Introduce the concept of organizing ideas in essays and compositions early in the education system, starting from junior secondary school classes. Develop age-appropriate activities and resources to help students develop strong organizational skills in their writing.

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